

8T – The Coupling Constants Series and Probability

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July 10, 2021

Abstract:

By analyzing the primorial equation from an angle of probability, that is by associating each prime a certain parameter, it is possible to reason for rarity of events, the longer we develop, the more rare and less likable to locate the boson. That given by the nature of the primorial.

Introduction

First, we can represent the original equation, which regard Bosonic fields to be net curvature on the varying Lorentz manifold. Those Bosons are isomorphic to prime numbers or one - $\mathbb{P} \cup (+1)$, and propagating from matter clusters destabilized by the majestic (3), which is the electron, from the second element and above. Associate a probability of certain sort to the first element, $N_V = (+3)$. the majestic three and the invariant multiplier eight will be presented as a constants, \mathcal{M} , \mathcal{K} .

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \tag{1}$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \tag{1.1}$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \tag{1.2}$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \cup (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \cup (+1); P_{max} \in \mathbb{P}$$

$$8 + (1):(24 + (3)) + 3:(120 + (3)) + 5:(840 + (3)) + 7... \tag{1.21}$$

Correlating the net curvature element to a certain probability.

$$N_V = (+3) \rightarrow P(A) \quad (2)$$

$$P(A) < 1$$

Now, for simplicity sake assume that the probability is the same for all each higher element in the series. As we do not really know what is the probability of such an event, it is possible to assume that is the case. We can represent the equation in means of probability.

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) + \mathcal{M} \right) + P(A) \quad (2.1)$$

$$A \in \mathbb{P};$$

For each higher term than there is a dependence, the next element in the series can only arise after a previous probability was satisfied, as it is a series. So the longer we develop, the smaller the probability to detect the boson as it is depended upon longer chain of events, with probability smaller than one. We can represent it in a simpler fashion by ignoring the constants:

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \quad (3)$$

Let $A \rightarrow \infty$

$$P_A\# = \left(K * \prod_{A=3}^{A=2n+1} P(A) \right) \rightarrow 0 \quad (3.1)$$

Such a representation of the primorial series than makes it easier to understand how hard it will be to detect those higher term coupling bosons, and why they have not found up to this day. However, if scientists have detected gravitational waves they should be able to detect the next elements in the coupling series, as they are about seven, and seventy two weaker than the electric. Therefore, despite each term is an individual element which have a unique boson isomorphic to \mathbb{P} for the second and above, there is an implicit dependence given by the fact that is a mathematical series and each even sum is a scalar multiple of the next prime. If we represent the series from an angle of the arrow of time, the higher the coupling term, the more time it will need to develop it. Weakest interactions appear than after longer periods of time, and the strongest most common ones appear at the beginning. We can make a prediction:

(1) The probability of locating the boson of the third term is significantly higher than the sixth term.

References

- [1] O. Manor. "8 Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)
- [2] O. Manor. "The Coupling constants series, Spin Symmetries and Unbounded electrons" In: (2021)